

**PERSONALLY-HELD MEANING OF
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ACTION RESEARCH**

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Personally-Held Meaning of English-Specialized Secondary Master Teachers Towards Action Research

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Abstract

This case study explored the personally-held meaning of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers towards action research, examined their action research productivity, and analyzed the expectation and pressure to produce high-quality action research on their experiences and practices. It utilized a semi-structured interview, and transcripts were scrutinized using thematic analysis. The study found that teachers view action research as a transformative process that promotes reflective practice and self-awareness and strengthens their professional competence. However, the study also revealed that English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers face challenges in allocating time for action research due to their extensive teaching and non-teaching responsibilities. As regards external pressures and expectations, teachers emphasized the value of adopting a growth mindset and perceiving action research as an ongoing learning process. It is recommended that educational institutions and policymakers consider the time constraints faced by teachers and provide adequate support, resources, and professional development opportunities to enhance their engagement in action research.

Keywords: *english-specialized secondary master teachers, action research, case study, DepEd*

Introduction

The implementation of the DepEd Research Agenda (DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016) and the Basic Education Research Fund (DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2015, DepEd No. 24, s. 2010) has sought to foster a culture of action research among DepEd employees especially teachers, emphasizing the importance of conducting action research for both classroom problem-solving and professional development.

Action research is widely acknowledged as a potent instrument for enhancing the quality of teaching and learning within the educational system (Burns, 2014). Furthermore, it serves as a significant criterion for career advancement (Ulla, Barrera, & Acompañado, 2017), particularly for those aspiring to become Master Teachers.

However, despite the implementation of these DepEd initiatives aimed at institutionalizing action research in basic education, it appears that these programs have not adequately addressed the issue of low research productivity among teachers (Enerio, 2020; Tindowen, Guzman, & Macanang, 2019; Salcedo-Relucio, 2019; Mapa, 2017). Teachers in the basic education are currently in the process of adapting and incorporating action research into their educational practices, indicating that it is still a relatively new concept within their professional culture. (Tindowen, Guzman, & Macanang, 2019).

Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate teachers' perspectives on action research, the challenges they encountered, and the factors affecting lower action research productivity (Abrenica & Cascolan, 2022; Cortes & Reyes, 2021, Anzaldo & Cudiamat (2019); Salcedo-Relucio, 2019; Tindowen, Guzman, & Macanang, 2019; Ulla, 2018). Notably, these studies involved participants in lower positions such as Teacher I-III, whose motivation for conducting action research may be driven by aspirations for promotion ((Ulla, Barrera, & Acompañado, 2017),). While Enerio (2020) conducted a study involving Master Teachers' challenges in conducting action research, the participants were elementary Master Teachers who do not have specific areas of specialization. In contrast, the current study focuses on secondary Master Teachers specializing in the field of English, thereby presenting a unique perspective.

English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers may hold diverse perspectives on the conduct of action research. Some may perceive it as a relatively straightforward task, given their expertise in language teaching and proficiency in writing. However, others may view it as a burdensome responsibility, considering the potential stereotype associated with their role as English Master Teachers, wherein they are expected to excel in producing well-written action research projects. As to what perspectives do secondary English Master Teachers in Tanguib City hold, these are yet to be revealed.

Master Teachers are expected to have periodically

conducted action research as it is a mandated requirement in their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form. However, there remains a noticeable hesitance or perceived distance in engaging in this research practice as evidenced by Enerio's (2020) study, which found that out of five Master Teachers in the school, only one successfully completed an action research project.

Research Questions

In light of the aforementioned issues, the purpose of this study is to explore and understand the personally held meaning of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers in the Division of Tanguib City towards action research. Specifically, the research aims to address the following questions:

1. What is the personally held meaning of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers towards action research in terms of personal and professional development?
2. What do English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers have to say regarding their productivity in conducting action research?
3. How does the expectation and pressure for English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers to produce high-quality action research influence their experiences and practices?

Literature Review

Research serves as a driving force in education reform, enabling progress and guidance for decision-making skills (Briones, 2022). She furthered that through the utilization of tools like the one mentioned, one can refine outputs, make better decisions, devise improved programs, and identify areas that are ripe for improvement. This ongoing process of research and analysis is essential in fostering a continuously evolving and effective educational system. Action research in the field of education encompasses the application of action research in formal and informal educational settings, both at local and global levels (ALARA, 2015). Action research is a form of research acknowledged for its focus on reflective methods, with the goal of improving professional classroom learning by implementing targeted measures (Irwandi et al., 2019). Action research is a systematic approach wherein an educator identifies issues within their own classroom setting and proceeds to employ investigative techniques to resolve those issues (De Beer, 2019).

Action research serves the purpose of addressing

actual classroom issues. This research endeavor not only focuses on problem-solving but also seeks scientific solutions to drive improvement (Palmer & Jacobson, 2009; Djaali, 2004). Action research typically aims to achieve two primary objectives: (1) fostering a research-oriented culture among educational staff to encourage proactivity, and (2) promoting collaboration among educators to address learning challenges. By conducting action research effectively, teachers are expected to develop the competence to resolve problems and make informed decisions in the teaching and learning process (Irwandi et al., 2019).

Hence, teachers must possess the skill of writing scientific papers as one of their competencies. As a result, they need to be capable of conducting action research to enhance the quality of learning and professionalism. Furthermore, teachers should also communicate the outcomes of innovative teaching practices to the professional community. Professional educators are those who consistently enhance their competence, exhibit creativity and innovation, and evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of their teaching and learning practices, primarily through action research. Engaging in action research offers numerous advantages for teachers, ultimately leading to the enhancement of the learning process's quality (Irwandi et al., 2019).

Action research is a progressive approach aimed at comprehending a problem and generating knowledge through various means such as observation, active listening, analysis, questioning, and the construction of knowledge (Carr & Kemmis, 2010; Andreas, 2000; Burns, 1999; Elliot, 1992). This kind of research is conducted through a methodical inquiry, with an enduring and ongoing nature, serving as a critical assessment (Ratnawati & Idris, 2020; Suwandi, 2013; Burns, 1999). This implies that action research in the classroom involves the teacher as a researcher, engaging in a continuous process of systematic investigation. While the teacher can conduct action research in segmented parts, the essence of continuity lies in utilizing the research findings over time. This is because each group possesses unique characteristics, and even if the problem is identical, the approaches employed may differ (Irwandi et al., 2019).

However, studies indicated that there is a need to enhance teachers' proficiency in writing scientific sentences. Their knowledge and skills in implementing research are still insufficient, as demonstrated by the lack of exploration and study of theoretical foundations. Additionally, teachers face challenges in

accessing relevant literature due to limited internet and library resources. To address these issues, it is recommended that school management implement specific policies and activities to enhance teachers' ability to conduct action research and effectively disseminate research outcomes in a professional manner. Furthermore, it is crucial to improve teachers' competence in utilizing scientific language and elevate the quality of theoretical sources by referencing reputable journals (Akande, 2021; Irwandi et al., 2019; Morales et al., 2016). It is also notable for citing how teachers need assistance every step of the way in conducting and writing action research despite their ability to have known the problems in the classroom and their possible solutions (Enerio, 2020).

Moreover, the existing paradigm of teacher professional development places importance on students' productivity and highlights the need for teachers to acquire knowledge, understanding, and the ability to apply that knowledge in curriculum development, teaching methodologies, and assessment (Petrovska et al., 2018; Rutherford & Lovorn, 2018). Furthermore, it advocates for the encouragement of teachers to engage in self-practice and construct new knowledge and skills, rather than relying solely on traditional models where teachers passively receive learning from external experts (Sumaryanta et al., 2019; Makovec, 2018).

Research findings have demonstrated that classroom action research serves as an effective approach in bridging the gap between theory and practice in teacher development within various contexts (Ratnawati & Idris, 2020; Irwandi et al., 2019; De Beer, 2019; Bissonnette & Caprino, 2014;). It aligns with the objective of education management, which encourages teachers to engage in research and utilize classroom action research as a means of professional development (Meesuk et al., 2019). Teaching is recognized as a distinguished profession requiring scientific knowledge and artistic skills. Therefore, it is crucial to elevate the professional standards of teachers, regardless of their affiliations, through sustainable and equitable development (Meesuk, 2016). Action research is an essential responsibility of teachers, undertaken alongside managing learning, to systematically enhance their own growth and that of their students (Wongwanich, 2017). The reviewed pieces of literature have substantiated that action research is beneficial for both the teacher and the learners. However, there is little to no study that investigated the perception of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers towards action research, their experiences thereof, or the lack of it. Hence, the

researcher found it relevant to conduct the present study.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design employed in this study is qualitative in nature and aims to explore and understand the fundamental nature of human experiences among the study participants (Creswell, 2014). Specifically, the research follows a case study design, which involves examining the experiences of a particular population by analyzing a central case (Stake, 1995). In this case, the focus is on studying English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers as a collective entity, analyzing their experiences within the context of action research. The aim is to develop a descriptive analysis of these experiences that can be applicable to the specific unit of study (Stake, 1995). The decision to utilize the case study approach was motivated by the study's objective to reveal overarching interpretations that can be applied to various situations, even if there are differences in the specific details provided by the participants.

Research Setting

The researcher conducted the study in the Division of Tangub City located in the province of Misamis Occidental. Tangub City serves as one of the three capital cities in the region geographically surrounded by the Malindang Mountains to the north, Panguil Bay to the south, Ozamiz City to the east, and the municipality of Bonifacio to the west. The Department of Education (DepEd), Division of Tangub City was initially established as an Interim Division in June 2003. However, in February 2008, it was officially upgraded to a full-fledged Division within Region 10, following an order issued by the then Secretary of Education Jesli A. Lapus.

Sampling

The participants in this research are the four English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers of the different secondary schools in Tangub City Division namely, Tangub City National High School (Master Teacher II), Sumirap National High School (Master Teacher II), Lorenzo Tan National High School (Master Teacher I), and Sta. Maria National High School (Master Teacher I).

Data Collection

In order to collect the data, the researcher contacted four Secondary Master Teachers who specialized in English via email, inviting them to participate in the study. The letter conveyed the purpose of the research and outlined the procedures for data collection. Alongside the letter, a Google Form was provided, containing interview questions for the participants to answer. However, the responses obtained through the Google Form were relatively limited. Consequently, the researcher followed up with the participants via email, requesting their participation in an online interview at their convenience. The researcher utilized the online messaging app, Messenger to facilitate communication during this process.

Fortunately, the participants agreed to engage in the study. Due to their varying availability, it was not feasible to conduct a focus group discussion. Instead, individual semi-structured interviews were conducted online using Google Meet. Each interview lasted between 30 to 50 minutes. Following the interviews, the recorded responses were transcribed verbatim. To ensure the accuracy of the transcriptions, the researcher meticulously reviewed the transcripts against the recorded interviews, undertaking the transcription personally. The transcriptions were subsequently shared with the participants for verification and to allow for any necessary corrections. This iterative process aimed to enhance the authenticity and validity of the gathered data. Finally, the data were subjected to an inductive and thematic analysis.

Data Analysis

The data collected in this study underwent thematic analysis, which involved analyzing similar data related to the research topic and providing relevant insights. The first step in the data analysis process was organizing the data, where each interview was carefully reviewed and the transcripts were checked for accuracy. Each participant's interview transcript was then analyzed using established data analysis procedures, including the development of coding categories, sorting the data systematically, and analyzing the data within each coding category. This coding process was conducted separately for each participant's interview, involving three steps: defining categories, providing examples, and establishing coding regulations. Firstly, meaningful categories were created, named, and assigned codes based on the answers to each question. Secondly, the conceptualized statements were gathered and examined collectively. Finally, each statement was carefully reviewed to avoid repetition. In the final

phase of the analysis, the identified results were explained and interconnected to establish meaningful relationships between them.

Ethical Considerations

All participants were requested to provide their voluntary participation in the research by signing the consent form, which was included in the letter sent via email. The consent form explicitly emphasized that their personal identities would remain undisclosed, and anonymous codes would be used to ensure confidentiality. In particular, participants were not obligated to disclose their full names in the questionnaire, and all collected data, including videos and recordings, were securely stored using coded filenames to prevent unauthorized access. Participants were also informed of their right to decline answering certain questions during the interview and had the freedom to terminate the interview at any point if they felt uncomfortable. Moreover, participants were assured that their involvement would not result in any harm, and the study findings would be strictly utilized for academic purposes. Throughout the study, the researcher diligently adhered to the provisions stipulated by the Republic Act 10173, commonly referred to as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. This legislation aims to safeguard the fundamental human right to privacy and communication, while simultaneously facilitating the unfettered exchange of information to encourage innovation and growth.

Results and Discussion

There were three problems identified in this study: What is the personally held meaning of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers towards action research in terms of personal and professional development? What do English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers have to say regarding their productivity in conducting action research? And how does the expectation and pressure for English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers to produce high-quality action research influence their experiences and practices? After conducting a thematic analysis, five distinct themes were identified, providing insights that address the three research problems at hand.

- Action research fosters reflective practice and self-awareness;
- Action research strengthens their professional competence.
- Their extensive teaching and other non-teaching

responsibilities often limited the amount of time they could allocate to conducting action research.

- They emphasized the significance of focusing on personal growth and professional development rather than solely aiming to meet external standards.
- They believed in embracing a growth mindset and viewing action research as a continuous learning process.

What is the personally held meaning of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers towards action research in terms of personal and professional development?

Theme 1: Action research fosters reflective practice and self-awareness.

English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers generally ascribe similar personal meanings to action research in terms personal development. They view action research as an opportunity to engage in reflective practice and deepen their understanding of their own strengths and areas for improvement. They perceive action research as a transformative process that enhances their self-awareness, promotes lifelong learning, and contributes to their personal growth. They value the self-reflective nature of action research, recognizing its potential to expand their understanding of their own teaching practices. Furthermore, they express a strong connection between action research and personal empowerment. They view it as a means to take ownership of their personal development, enabling them to develop a sense of agency and control over their own growth, leading to increased job satisfaction and fulfillment.

Theme 2: Action research strengthens their professional competence.

English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers also attribute significant meaning to action research in terms of their professional development. One prevailing theme is the perception that action research strengthens their professional competence. They regarded action research as a means to advance professionally, and an opportunity to deepen their understanding of pedagogical practices, enhance their teaching skills, and expand their knowledge of the English language. They perceive it as a means to continuously improve their own instructional strategies and to better meet the needs of their students. They appreciate the chance to critically analyze their teaching methods, identify areas for improvement, and develop targeted interventions to address student learning challenges. Master Teachers believe that action research strengthens their professional

competence, builds their expertise, and positions them as reflective practitioners committed to ongoing professional growth.

What do English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers have to say regarding their productivity in conducting action research?

Theme 3: Their extensive teaching and other non-teaching responsibilities often limited the amount of time they could allocate to conducting action research.

English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers faced significant constraints in allocating time for action research due to their extensive teaching and non-teaching responsibilities. These teachers are often burdened with a range of tasks, including lesson planning, curriculum development, administrative duties, and extracurricular activities. As a result, their already demanding schedules left them with limited time and energy to devote to conducting action research. The teachers expressed frustration at the challenge of balancing their teaching responsibilities with the additional workload associated with action research. They emphasized that the time-consuming nature of action research, including data collection, analysis, and reflection, required substantial dedication. However, the demands of their teaching roles often took precedence, leaving them with limited opportunities to engage fully in the research process. Furthermore, the non-teaching responsibilities, such as attending meetings, training sessions, and other administrative tasks, further diminished the time available for action research. These additional responsibilities, although important for overall school functioning, added to the already limited time teachers had for conducting research.

How does the expectation and pressure for English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers to produce high-quality action research influence their experiences and practices?

Theme 4: They emphasized the significance of focusing on personal growth and professional development rather than solely aiming to meet external standards.

English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers expressed a belief that their professional journey should be driven by a commitment to continuous improvement and a genuine desire to enhance their teaching practice. The teachers acknowledged the

existence of external standards and expectations, such as those set by educational institutions or governing bodies. However, they emphasized the need to strike a balance between meeting these standards and pursuing personal and professional growth on their own terms. They viewed action research as a means to delve deeper into their teaching methodologies, experiment with innovative approaches, and explore new ways to meet the unique needs of their students. By focusing on personal growth and professional development, teachers expressed a desire to challenge themselves beyond the requirements set by external standards. They sought opportunities for self-reflection, experimentation, and creative problem-solving, which allowed them to evolve as educators and adapt their instructional practices to best serve their students' learning needs.

Theme 5: They believed in embracing a growth mindset and viewing action research as a continuous learning process.

This theme highlights the emphasis placed by English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers on embracing a growth mindset and perceiving action research as a continuous learning process. They recognized that adopting a growth mindset was crucial for their professional development. They believed that their abilities and skills were not fixed but could be developed through effort, learning, and experience. They acknowledged that engaging in action research allowed them to expand their knowledge, refine their teaching practices, and enhance their overall effectiveness as educators. By viewing action research as a continuous learning process, teachers embraced the idea that their research endeavors were not limited to a singular project or outcome. Instead, they saw each research cycle as an opportunity for ongoing learning and improvement. Teachers expressed the significance of reflecting on their research findings and using them as a basis for refining their instructional approaches. They understood that action research provided a platform for self-reflection and critical analysis of their teaching practices. Through this reflective process, they were able to identify areas of strength, areas in need of improvement, and innovative strategies to better support their students' learning.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of this study shed light on the personally held meanings of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers towards growth among

teachers can be further cultivated, ultimately benefiting the educational outcomes of students and the field of English education as a whole practice, self-awareness, and personal empowerment. They value the opportunity to deepen their understanding of pedagogical practices, enhance their teaching skills, and expand their knowledge of the English language. Furthermore, they attribute significant meaning to action research in terms of their professional competence, recognizing its role in continuous improvement and advancing their expertise as educators.

However, the study also revealed that the extensive teaching and non-teaching responsibilities of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers pose significant constraints on their ability to allocate time for action research. Balancing their teaching obligations with the demands of action research proved challenging, as limited time and energy hindered their full engagement in the research process. Non-teaching responsibilities further added to their time constraints, leaving them with limited opportunities for research activities.

Despite these challenges, the teachers emphasized the significance of focusing on personal growth and professional development, rather than solely aiming to meet external standards. They highlighted the importance of embracing a growth mindset and perceiving action research as a continuous learning process. By doing so, they sought opportunities for self-reflection, experimentation, and collaboration, which allowed them to evolve as educators and adapt their instructional practices to better serve their students' needs.

The findings of this study contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the experiences and practices of English-specialized Secondary Master Teachers in relation to action research. It is recommended that educational institutions and policymakers consider the time constraints faced by teachers and provide adequate support, resources, and professional development opportunities to enhance their engagement in action research. By doing so, the potential for personal and professional action research in terms of personal and professional development. The teachers perceive action research as a transformative process that fosters reflective.

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